

What is NFDI4Cat?

NFDI4Cat is a community-driven and user-oriented initiative to secure the digital future of catalysis.

Development of catalysis-specific vocabularies

Language vocabularies

A collection of words and phrases within a language used and understood in speaking a writing.

- Words are attributed a meaning (definition). A word's meaning is the same for everyone → allows communication.
- Readable and understandable by humans in different contexts.
- Easily searchable by humans → alphabetized in a dictionary form.
- Vocabularies evolve or are expanded over time.

Vocabularies on the Semantic Web

Vocabularies define the concepts and relationships used to describe and represent an area of concern.

- Application-specific concepts and definitions.
- Classification and standardization of terms.
- Description of relationships between concepts.
- Vocabularies can be updated as the specific field evolves.
- Machine readable and understandable → **FAIR**^(*) data.
- A vocabulary should be formal, explicit and shared.

A community-driven and user-oriented initiative.

(*) **FAIR**: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable. M. D. Wilkinson et al., Sci Data 3, 160018 (2016), p. 331-349

Collection of concepts

The developed vocabulary supports the creation of and translation into the concepts used in ontologies by providing the explicit definitions used for these concepts.

For the development of the vocabularies in NFDI4Cat, the VocExcel (Surround Australia Pty Ltd.) template was adapted and extended resulting in a more universal tool. components. This allows for simple data entry, as direct connections (dashed arrows) from the reaction to components are logically inferred by a reasoner. The reaction conditions are modeled as data properties; however, their modeling is not shown here for simplicity.

The developed vocabularies include a variety of concepts and their definitions describing the most often referenced terms in the scientific literature in the fields of homogeneous and heterogeneous (bio-) catalysis and reactor engineering. The extended template allows for the specification of a Preferred Label (standardized name for a concept), *Alternate Labels* (Other names for a concept), for *Children – Parent relations and Related – Close – Exact – Narrower – Broader* matches between concepts.

Voc4Cat guidelines

The VoG4Cat guidelines have been developed as a blueprint towards suggesting, adding, and editing content to the vocabularies developed throughout NFDI4Cat.

The aim of VoG4Cat is to provide guidelines to guarantee consistency and coherence on selection of concepts and terms between all catalysis-related vocabularies in NFDI4Cat.

VoG4Cat, initially inspired by the AGROVOC editorial guidelines of FAO,^[1] evolved over the course of Task Area 1 (TA1): *Ontology Development and Metadata Standards* of NFDI4Cat.

VoG4Cat includes guidelines for (among others): spelling variants, hyphenation, punctuation, abbreviations, writing chemical compounds and elements etc.

Vocabulary contribution workflow

A vocabulary contribution workflow has been developed that allows an easy integration of contribution from the catalysis community members.

Contributions (for concrete new vocabularies or changes to already existing ones) can be submitted (create a “merge request”) as an Excel file. Then the CI pipeline starts automatically, and when it is completed without errors a peer review and discussion process takes place. This peer review is followed by an approval stage by the editor, before the proposed change is “merged” and a updated vocabulary can be published.

„This study was conducted in connection to our activities in the project “Digitalization in Catalysis”
NFDI4Cat – ID: 441926934 funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation).“

